

Reference code for Estimation of Dual Permeability Model Parameters in Agricultural Fields using a Genetic Algorithm-Based Framework

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March 6, 2025

1 Simulation-optimization framework

Hydrus-1D is used for simulating the flow with varying set of parameters. The present study employed open-source python library, PyGAD for optimization.

Inputs and Model Setup

The following setup and parameters were used for this study:

- **Units:** Centimeters (cm) and days.

- **Simulation time window:** 102 days.
- **Soil profile:** A 200 cm deep soil column.
- **Soil Hydraulic Properties (SHPs):** Silty loam (Estimated experimentally).
- **Boundary conditions (BCs):**
 - *Upper boundary condition:* Atmospheric boundary condition with surface layer.
 - *Lower boundary condition:* Free drainage.
- **Initial condition:** As discussed in the manuscript.
- **Observed Node:** 4 nodes at 10cm, 25cm, 50cm and 80cm.
- **Crop data:** Wheat crop data at IIT Kanpur site has been used (optional)

We utilized the HYDRUS-1D graphical user interface (GUI) to create the reference project. The project file is located in the directory C:\.

Modification in SELECTOR.IN file

Python Code Example

Below is the Python function `DPM_warming`, which was used for hydrological simulations.

Importing Libraries and Setting Paths

This block imports essential libraries and defines reference folders for the simulation.

```
import os
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from shutil import copyfile
import pygad

hydrus_exec = 'C:\H1D_Dual.exe'
ref_folder = 'C:\Field_DPM'
```

Listing 1: Importing Libraries and Setting Paths

Setting up Simulation Files

This function copies necessary HYDRUS reference files into the simulation folder, where the execution takes place. Creates the input files for HYDRUS executive. Copies the mandatory file Profile.dat to the corresponding folder and creates the corresponding Selector.in.

```
sim_folder = 'C:\\Simulated_data\\Field_DPM'
def setup_simulation_files(ref_folder, sim_folder):
    """Set up the simulation folder by copying required files."""
    os.makedirs(sim_folder, exist_ok=True)
    files_to_copy = ['PROFILE.DAT', 'SELECTOR.IN', 'ATMOSPH.IN']
    for file_name in files_to_copy:
        src = os.path.join(ref_folder, file_name)
        dest = os.path.join(sim_folder, file_name)
        if os.path.exists(src):
            copyfile(src, dest)
```

Listing 2: Setting up Simulation Files

Modifying SELECTOR.IN File

This function modifies the SELECTOR.IN file to adjust simulation parameters. The file is different for each simulation since the required parameters are variable in simulation- optimization framework. The code reads the reference Selector.in, copies the first 28 lines to the new file, write the van Genuchten parameters to the 27th line, and finally copies the last 10 lines from the reference Selector.in to the new file.

```
def modify_selector_file(sim_folder, param):
    file_path = os.path.join(sim_folder, 'SELECTOR.IN')
    with open(file_path, 'r') as file:
        lines = file.readlines()
    lines[26] = f'0.105 {param[0]:.3f} {param[1]:.4f} {param[2]:.3f} {
        param[3]:.3f} 0.500\n'
    with open(file_path, 'w') as file:
        file.writelines(lines)
```

Listing 3: Modifying SELECTOR.IN File

Model Execution and Simulation Processing

This function runs the HYDRUS simulation by calling its executable and processing the results. Once the simulation completes, it processes the output data generated by HYDRUS and extracts results by defining a function named `postprocess_simulated_data` for a chosen number of nodes.

```

def Model(ref_folder, hydrus_exec, sim_folder, param, num_nodes):
    setup_simulation_files(ref_folder, sim_folder)
    modify_selector_file(sim_folder, param)
    # Run HYDRUS executable
    exec_path = f'{hydrus_exec} {sim_folder}'
    os.system(exec_path)
    return postprocess_simulated_data(sim_folder, num_nodes)

```

Listing 4: Model Execution and Simulation Processing

Fitness Function for Genetic Algorithm

The fitness function evaluates how well the simulation results match observed data.

```

def fitness_func(ga_instance, solution, solution_idx):
    simulated = Model(ref_folder, hydrus_exec, sim_folder, solution, 4)
    return 1.0 / (sum(np.sum((simulated[i] - obs[i])**2) for i, obs in
        enumerate([theta_10_obs, theta_25_obs, theta_50_obs, theta_80_obs])
        ) + 1e-6)

```

Listing 5: Fitness Function for Genetic Algorithm

Genetic Algorithm Framework and Execution

This section sets up and runs the genetic algorithm to optimize simulation parameters.

```

gene_space = [{'low': 0.31, 'high': 0.45}, {'low': 0.009, 'high': 0.01}, {'
    'low': 1.47, 'high': 2},
    {'low': 0.2, 'high': 4}]
last_fitness = 0

def on_generation(ga_instance):
    global last_fitness
    best_fitness = ga_instance.best_solution(pop_fitness=ga_instance.
        last_generation_fitness)[1]
    print(f"Generation {ga_instance.generations_completed} | Fitness: {
        best_fitness} | Change: {best_fitness - last_fitness}")
    last_fitness = best_fitness

ga_instance = pygad.GA(num_generations=300, random_seed=100,
    num_parents_mating=10, sol_per_pop=12, num_genes=4,
        fitness_func=fitness_func, save_solutions=True,
        gene_space=gene_space, crossover_type="uniform",
        crossover_probability=0.8, mutation_type="random",
        mutation_probability=0.5, on_generation=
            on_generation)

ga_instance.run()

```

Listing 6: Genetic Algorithm Framework and Execution